

H1 histone as a potential *in vitro* biological dosimeter^ψ

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In 0.9% sodium chloride, pH range 7.3–7.4, A230 nm values for H1 histone (conc. 200 µg/ml) decrease upto 20 and 75 Gy at the dose rate of 0.0135 and 2.25 Gy/s, respectively linearly. Considerable dose rate dependency is not observed. In 0.01 N HCl, pH range 6.05–6.30, A230 nm values of H1 histone (conc. 200 µg/ml) increase with dose linearly upto 12 Gy at the dose rates of 0.0135 and 0.0504 Gy/s. Dose rate dependency is not found.

Fluorescence intensity of H1 histone (conc. 50 µg/ml) in EDTA buffer increases with radiation dose upto 100 Gy. When excited at 278 nm, increase in fluorescence intensity is three times at 350 nm compared to that at 305 nm for unirradiated solution and upto a dose of 100 Gy. The increase in fluorescence intensity at 305 and 350 nm reaches a shoulder from 50 upto 100 Gy. There is an increase in pH with increase in dose in a consistent fashion.

H1 histone (conc. 200 µg/ml) is found to be stable in the unirradiated 2.5 and 5 Gy for six days when irradiated at a dose rate of 0.0135 Gy/s, in the pH range 7.76–8.00 (the maximum percentage variation being less than 10%). So, H1 histone can be used as a potential *in vitro* biological dosimeter.

H1 histone occurs as a linker in the nucleosome and binds to the outside of the core and the linker DNA¹. Several types of H1 histones have been found and their biological functions reported². As this is a linker histone and present stereospecifically in the periphery of nucleosome it is likely to be sensitive to radiation dose. But dose response relationship especially under physiological pH at different dose rates have not been reported. Accidental radiation leakage measurement by *in vitro* biological dosimeter is important. Hence this work was undertaken.

Results and Discussion

H1 histone (conc. 25 µg/ml) showed λ_{\max} at 230 and 280 nm in EDTA buffer (pH 7.0), at 280 nm in phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and at 280 nm in standard saline citrate (SSC) buffer (pH 7.0), but did not show any absorption 0.9% NaCl (pH 6.5). H1 histone (conc. 20 µg/ml) showed consistent increase in absorbance intensity from 0.40 to 1.35 at 205 nm with increase in pH from 3.56 to 11.13. Moreover, at conc. 50 µg/ml and at pH 7.05, H1 histone showed minimum chromophoricity at 230 and 280 nm.

The absorbance maximum for H1 histone has been reported at 230 and 280 nm³. The value of the absorbance is 1.85 (where $c = 1$ mg/ml) at 230 nm. The absorbance of H1 histone at (i) 205, (ii) 220–240, (iii) 210–220 and (iv) 275–280 nm are due to (i) imidazole group of histidine, (ii) peptide bond, (iii) tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine⁴.

Acid hydrolysis of peptide bonds and release of amino

acids leading to absorption at 230 and 280 nm took place from H1 histone. With increase in pH, increase of imidazole group took place at 205 nm. Minimum chromophoricity at pH 7.05 indicates minimum hydrolysis of peptide bonds and availability of other chromophores like tyrosine, tryptophan and phenylalanine. Change in configuration with pH is possible which may induce chromophore exposition or suppression⁵. The extinction coefficient at 205 nm per peptide bond is in the range⁴ 2500–2800. So the absorbance intensity has increased in this wavelength region depending upon pH.

H1 histone showed linearity in absorbance at 230 nm upto 240 (pH 6.20–6.40), at 660 nm upto 140 (pH 6.5–7.5) and upto 200 µg/ml (pH 7.4–7.9) by Folin ciocalteau reagent. In the pH range 6.20–6.40, peptide bonds have increased proportionally with concentration thereby increasing A230 nm value upto 240 µg/ml. The linearity from 140 µg/ml (pH range 6.50–7.50) and upto 200 µg/ml (pH range 7.40–7.9) by Folin ciocalteau reagent is a clear indication of formation of copper-protein complex. The dissociation of this complex is pH-dependent⁶.

For H1 histone with increase in dose there was a consistent increase in fluorescence intensity when excited at 278 nm. The fluorescence intensity at 350 nm was found to be almost three times compared to that at 305 nm upto 80 Gy. A consistent increase in pH was also observed with dose (Table 1). The quantum yield of histones fluorescence is pH-dependent⁷. The fluorescence yield is due to the

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Note

ionisation of tyrosine residue. H1 histone has two tyrosine residues in the region containing the globular head⁸. Tyrosine is buried in the hydrophobic core. Depending upon pH the additional tyrosine residue got more exposed to the solvent than the one inside the core, thereby increasing the fluorescence intensity with pH (Table 1). Quantum yield at 305 and 350 nm varied with gamma radiation dose at these two emission maximum⁷.

Table 1. Fluorescence intensity of H1 histone as a function of gamma radiation dose

Conc. = 50 µg/ml. Solvent : EDTA 2.5×10^{-4} M, Ex = 278 nm, Dose rate = 0.0135 Gy/s

Dose Gy	Fluorescence intensity		pH
	At 305 nm	At 350 nm	
Unirr.	6.45	16.95	6.00
2	7.35	23.20	6.24
4	8.25	24.50	6.30
10	8.75	30.70	6.48
20	9.35	33.25	6.54
50	10.35	34.50	6.55
80	12.05	35.00	6.77
100	19.10	36.00	6.90

A consistent linear decrease in absorbance intensity of H1 histone (conc. 200 µg/ml) prepared in 0.9% sodium chloride at 230 nm upto 20 Gy for a dose rate of 0.0135 Gy/s and upto 75 Gy for a dose rate of 2.25 Gy/s was observed (Table 2). Decrease in absorbance intensity at 230 nm with dose of gamma irradiation is a clear indication of alteration of tertiary structure of H1 histone 90% folded but in water it is disordered⁹. The chromophores get hidden with dose. Even if there was a change in dose rate by an order of 200, the rate of decrease in A230 nm did not change considerably (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of gamma radiation on histone H1 at two different dose rates

Conc. = 200 µg/ml, pH = 7.3–7.4, Solvent : 0.9% NaCl

Dose (Gy)	Unirr.	Dose rate 0.0135 Gy/s :					
		2.5	5.0	7.5	10	15	20
A230 nm	0.73	0.70	0.69	0.68	0.67	0.66	0.63
Dose (Gy)	Unirr.	Dose rate 2.25 Gy/s :					
		25.75	30.25	50.50	64.00	75.00	
A230 nm	0.73	0.64	0.60	0.58	0.56	0.54	

H1 histone (conc. 200 µg/ml), when dissolved in 0.01 N HCl showed a linear increase in A230 nm values at the doses rates of 0.0135 Gy/s and 0.0504 Gy/s respectively up to 12 Gy (Table 3). Formation of chromophores from H1 histone for a fixed concentration of 200 µg/ml in 0.01 N HCl is independent of dose rate. Acid hydrolysis of peptide bond increased with radiation dose linearly upto 12 Gy (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of gamma irradiation on H1 histone at two different dose rates

Conc. = 200 µg/ml, pH = 6.05–6.30, Solvent : 0.01 N HCl

Dose Rate 0.0135 Gy/s		Dose Rate 0.0504 Gy/s	
Dose (Gy)	A230 nm	Dose (Gy)	A230 nm
Unirr.	0.60	Unirr.	0.60
1.5	0.68	1.0	0.66
3.0	0.80	2.0	0.70
6.0	0.84	4.0	0.74
8.0	1.00	6.0	0.84
10.0	1.10	8.0	0.98
12.0	1.20	10.0	1.08
		12.0	1.22

Table 4. Stability of H1 histone in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states

Dose rate = 0.0135 Gy/s, Solvent : 0.9% NaCl, pH = 7.76–8.00, Temp. = 25°

Unirr/Irr (Gy)	Absorbance values at 230 nm						Av. value ±Std. dev.	Max.% variation
	Days							
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Unirr.	0.73	0.83	0.80	0.77	0.87	0.62	0.80 ± 0.06	8.09
2.5	0.70	0.82	0.76	0.74	0.71	0.74	0.74 ± 0.02	9.85
5.0	0.69	0.77	0.73	0.78	0.74	0.63	0.72 ± 0.03	6.84
7.5	0.67	0.75	0.72	0.68	0.64	0.57	0.67 ± 0.03	11.38
10.0	0.65	0.71	0.71	0.63	0.58	0.53	0.63 ± 0.03	11.40
15.0	0.64	0.65	0.64	0.61	0.58	0.52	0.61 ± 0.02	7.80

H1 histone (conc. 200 µg/ml) was found to be stable in the unirradiated, 2.5 and 5 Gy for 6 days when irradiated at a dose rate of 0.0135 Gy/s in the pH range 7.76–8.00, the maximum percentage variation being less than 12% (Table 4). Maximum variation in A230 nm upto 5 Gy for a period of 6 days compared to unirradiated was found to be ~20%.

Experimental

Stock solutions of H1 histone (Lot No. 59 C, 8051, H 6881, Sigma) was prepared in 2.5×10^{-4} M EDTA, 0.15 M standard saline citrate or phosphate buffer or 0.9% sodium chloride solution. Folin ciocalteau reagent (CSIR) was added in requisite quantity to solutions of different histone concentrations to measure their absorbance values at 660 nm. Irradiation of solutions to desired doses were done in Gamma Cell 220 supplied by Atomic Energy of Canada (low dose rate) and Gamma Chamber 5000 supplied by Board of Radiation and Isotopes Technology, Mumbai (high dose rate) for attaining dose rates of 0.0135 and 2.25 Gy/s as determined by FBX¹⁰ and Fricke dosimetry¹¹. The solutions were kept in test tubes of uniform diameter in cold condition and placed in a circular geometry in either of the dosimetric chambers for a period of time as required for getting the desired absorbed dose. The absorbed dose uncertainty in the Gamma Cell 220 and Gamma Chamber 5000 were ±3 and ±10%, respectively, as determined by FBX and Fricke dosimetry, respectively. Absorbance,

fluorescence and pH measurements were done by Chemito 2500 UV-visible spectrophotometer, Aminco-Bowmann spectrophotofluorimeter and pH meter (Toshniwal), respectively.

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